

Navigating Tax Laws: Legal Insights for India's MSME Sector

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Abstract : Micro Small Medium Enterprises (MSME) are defined under the Micro Small Medium Enterprises Development Act, 2006. The enactment classifies the enterprises based on their amount of investment and annual turnover. MSMEs play a vital role in fostering innovation, growth and employment generation. MSMEs are eligible for a number of tax breaks. These tax breaks are provided by the government to promote entrepreneurship. This paper analyses both direct and indirect tax regimes to give a thorough legal review of the tax laws affecting MSMEs in India. The paper attempts to provide important insights into how India's tax environment affects the MSMEs

Keywords: MSME, Taxation, Entrepreneurship, Legal Framework, India

Introduction

Micro Small Medium Enterprises (MSME) play a crucial role in contributing to a country's economic development. MSMEs act as a stepping stone into entrepreneurship. There are 5.93 crores registered MSMEs employing more than 25 crore people. The enterprises are categorised into Micro Small Medium Enterprises based on the amount of investment and the turnover. The government enacted the Micro Small Medium Enterprises Development Act, 2006. MSMEs are considered as the catalyst to economic development and social development of developing countries.¹The objective of the enactment is to promote and develop Micro Small Medium Enterprises.

The government, in the budget of 2025 – 2026, has expanded the investment and turn over thresholds to strengthen the MSME sector recognising its contributions for the development of the country.

Revised classification criteria² –

	INVESTMENT	TURN OVER
CRO ENTERPRISE	CRORES	CRORES

¹ (Khan & Dalu,2015)

² Budget 2025-26, Ministry of Micro, Small Medium Enterprises

ALL ENTERPRISE	CRORES	CRORES
MEDIUM ENTERPRISE	CRORES	CRORES

Taxation Of Msme

To begin with, Tax is a country’s major source of income. A diversified tax system helps the country to generate more income and also spreads the tax burden on a large number of people. In India, we have two major types of taxes namely Direct Tax and Indirect Tax. The classification is based on the tax incidence and tax burden. In case of Direct Taxes, the tax incidence and tax burden falls on the same person whereas, in case of indirect taxes, the tax burden is shifted to another person.

With regard to MSME, the government levies both direct and indirect taxes on MSME. The government has given various tax benefits in order to promote MSMEs which shall be discussed below;-

Direct Tax –

Direct taxes are compulsory levy imposed by the governments on the assessee’s income. There are various direct taxes that affect MSMEs and the government also provides for notable tax incentives on the same.

1. Tax Holiday –

A tax holiday is a temporary exemption from paying taxes granted by the government to businesses, individuals and specific industries. This helps to promote entrepreneurship and economic growth. Such tax holidays helps MSMEs to develop and grow in their initial stages of business. Under section 80 IAC of Income Tax Act, 1961, a start up company can avail 100% tax exemption for a period of three consecutive years provided the annual turnover of the start up is less than 100crores in any financial year. In order to avail this benefit, the start up must have been incorporated with in 31st March 2026. The assessee can claim the deduction under this section for any three consecutive years within 7 years starting from the date of incorporation of the company.

The section provides for the following conditions in order to avail the deduction ; -

- i) The start up is not formed by splitting or reconstruction of an existing company.
- ii) It is not formed by the transfer to a new business of machinery or plant previously used for any purpose.

2. Investment allowance –

Under this section 32AC of the Income Tax Act,1961, if an assessee who is engaged in the business of manufacture or production of any article can claim for a deduction on the fulfilment of these conditions-

- i) The assessee has acquired a new asset
- ii) The actual cost of the asset exceeds Rs.100 crores
- iii) The asset has been acquired between 31st March 2013 and 1st April 2015.

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If the above conditions are satisfied, the assessee can claim a deduction of

- a) If the assets are acquired and installed between 31st March 2013 and 1st April 2014, a deduction of 15% of the actual cost of the asset for the assessment year commencing on 1st April 2014.
- b) If the assets are acquired and installed between 31st March 2013 and 1st April 2015, a deduction of 15% of the total cost of the acquired asset for the assessment year commencing on 1st April 2015.

Further, sub section (1A) of 32AC provides that if an assessee being a company acquires and installs any new asset in the previous year and the cost of the same exceeds Rs.25 crores, then the assessee can claim a deduction of 15% of the actual cost of the asset for the relevant assessment of the previous year provided, the asset has been acquired and installed on or before 31st March 2017. If the asset acquired was installed in any other year apart from the year of acquisition, then the deduction shall be claimed in the year in which the asset was installed. Sub section (1B) provides that no deduction can be claimed by the assessee for any assessment year commencing from 1st April 2018.

If the assets installed are transferred or sold, except by way of amalgamation or merger within the period of five years from the date of amalgamation, the deduction in respect of the asset shall be deemed to be the income of the assessee under the head profit and gains from business or profession of the previous year in which the asset was sold / transferred.

3. Reduction in Tax rate –

Section 115BA provides for a reduced tax rates at 25% to the companies for the previous year relevant to the assessment year after 1st April 2017 provide the company satisfies the following conditions;-

- a) The company is a domestic company
- b) The company is engaged in the business of manufacturing or production of an article or a thing
- c) The total income of the company is computed without the deductions,

The above provisions of the Act shall be applicable to an assessee only if the assessee has opted for the provision in the prescribed manner on or before the date specified under section 139(1) for furnishing the return of income and the preference cannot be withdrawn subsequently.

4. Capital gain exemption

As per Section 54GB of Income Tax Act, 1961, when an assessee being an individual or an Hindu Undivided Family transfers a long term capital asset which is a residential property either in the form of a house of a vacant plot and the capital gain arising out of the transfer is invested in the subscription of equity shares of a MSME within the due date of the filing of return of income under section 139 (1) , the capital gain will not be taxed in the hands of the assessee in the previous year if the following conditions are satisfied –

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- a. The MSME in which the assessee has invested in the equity shares must have utilised the amount in the purchase of a new asset within one year from the date of subscription.
- b. If the net consideration is not completely utilised for the purchase of the asset, the unutilised amount shall be taxable.
- c. The new asset purchased by the MSME or the equity shares should not be sold within a period of 5 years. In the case of sale or transfer, the exempted tax amount shall be taxed in the previous year of the transfer of the assets or the equity shares.
- d. In case, the new asset is a computer or a computer software, the asset should not be sold for three years.
- e. The provisions of this section shall not apply to any transfer of residential property made after the 31st day of March, 2022.

5. MSME Payment rule -

Section 43 B (h) was inserted in the Finance Act, 2023. The new clause provided for the timely payment for Micro or Small Enterprises. If the assessee who owes any payment to a Micro or Small enterprise makes the payment within the time stipulated under section 15 of Micro Small Medium Enterprises Development Act, 2006, the amount paid can be claimed as deduction after the actual payment.

Section 15 of MSMED Act, 2006 makes it mandatory to make the payment for Micro or Small Enterprises in the following manner ; -

- a) In case of a written agreement, 45 days from the date of acceptance or the due date specified in the agreement whichever is earlier.
- b) Within 15 days when there is no agreement.

This provision enables the MSEs to have a better working capital and manage cash flow.

6. Presumptive Tax – Section 44 AD of the Income Tax Act, 1961 provides that any assessee who is engaged in a business with a turnover not exceeding Rs. 2 crores, the assessee can calculate a presumptive tax at the rate of 8 % on non – digital transactions and 6% on digital transactions³.
7. Additional Depreciation - Under section 32 AD of Income Tax Act, MSMEs can claim an additional depreciation at 15% for specified good and services.

Indirect Tax

Goods and service Taxes (GST) is an indirect tax which has replaced the various taxes namely VAT, Service Tax etc from the old Indirect Tax regime. GST is governed by 4 major Acts namely Central Goods and Services Act, State Goods and Services Act, Integrated Goods and Services Act, Union Territory Goods and Services Act. GST has eliminated the cascading

³Presumptive Taxation And Practical Aspects A Critical Analysis Of Section 44 AD Of Income Tax Act

effect which was prevalent in the old tax regime of Indirect Taxes.

GST REGISTRATION -

In GST registration, the supplier is allotted a 15-digit GST identification number called “GSTIN” and a certificate of registration incorporating there in this GSTIN is made available to the applicant on the GSTN common portal. The first 2 digits of the GSTIN is the State code, next 10 digits are the PAN of the legal entity, the next two digits are for entity code, and the last digit is check sum number. Registration under GST is not tax specific which means that there is a single registration for all the taxes i.e. CGST, SGST/UTGST, IGST and cesses. Under section 22 of CGST Act, 2017, any business which is engaged in sale of goods with an aggregate turnover over Rs.40 crores shall be liable for GST registration. In case the business is carried on in a special category state, the threshold limit is Rs.20 crores. The service providers are liable to get their registration if the aggregate turnover is over Rs. 20 Crores and Rs.10 Crores in case of Special category states.

2. Composition Scheme

Section 10 of the CSGT Act provides for composition Levy. The scheme of Composition Levy is an alternative for the small business owners. A registered taxable person, whose aggregate turnover does not exceed Rs.1.50 Crore, as a supplier of goods or Rs.75 Lacs for business in special category states in the preceding financial year may opt for this scheme.

- (i) However, a supplier of services only (or services and goods together) with annual turnover up to ₹ 50 Lakh may opt for composition scheme and the rate of GST applicable for supplier would be 6%. The scheme helps small business owners with maintenance of minimal records and simplified returns.

3. Input Tax Credit (Itc) –

Section 16 of the CGST Act, 2017 provides for the eligibility and conditions for claiming ITC. Input Tax Credit allows the MSMEs to reduce their taxation by claiming the tax paid by them for the purchases used in their operations. ITC helps MSME business by cutting down the production and operational cost and helps to maintain liquidity in the business.

Table 1 - Provisions Under Income Tax Act, 1961

S.no	Section	Provision
1	80 IAC	Tax holiday for a period of three consecutive years
2	32AC	Investment allowance that provides a deduction of 15% of the total cost of the asset
3	115BA	Reduced tax rate at 25%
4	54GB	Capital Gain exemption helps MSME to
5	43 B (h)	MSME Payment rule
6	44 AD	Presumptive tax in the rate of 8 % and 6 % on non – digital and digital transactions respectively.

7	32 AD	Additional Depreciation of 15 %
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Table 2 – Provision Sunder The Goods And Service Tax, 2017

S.no	Section	Provision
1	22	GST registration is not mandatory for business with a turnover of Rs.40 crores
2	10	Composition Levy
3	16	Input Tax Credit which helps MSME to reduce their tax liability
4	Rule 54, CGST Rules	HSN codes in Tax invoice referred under section 31, CGST Act
5	Section 35 (5)	Audit by a chartered accountant is scrapped

Suggestions And Conclusion

MSMSEs in India has a crucial contribution to the country’s economic development and the government has taken few measures to boost the increase in MSMEs. The tax system in India provide for various tax benefits to support and promote MSMEs. However the cumbersome tax compliances are like multiple GST filings, delayed ITC post challenges to for small business owners. The small business mainly in rural areas do not have adequate knowledge on the tax benefits and the procedures to be complied by them. The government can conduct awareness programs for such rural small business owners for better clarity especially in their regional language. Overall the taxation policies in India has given various benefits to MSMEs and helps to the promotion and development of more such MSMEs. Apart from tax incentives, the government also provides for various schemes wherein the MSME business owners can take up loans with minimalist procedures.

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